

TWIN

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Twinning to build
an industrial
ecosystem

around the core
principles of
Industry 4.0 and
Digital Twins

Digital Twins

Big Data

Machine Learning

TWIN

PROJE

Twin4Twin aims to transfer know-how and decrease the expertise gap between partners in top-tier countries and CORE Innovation Centre (CORE IC), realising its vision of fostering an innovative industrial ecosystem.

ECT

Twin4Twin
is a project
supported by
the Horizon
Europe
Widening Work
Programme.

core|IC

CORE IC facilitates collaboration
between industry leaders and
research institutions by co-creating
and developing cutting-edge
Industry 4.0 Solutions.

4 F AREAS

FOCUS

to spread excellence
and achieve
economic growth

1. Digital Twins – Scientific Excellence

Transfer of know-how in
digital twin and big data
technologies to CORE IC

PhD and Internship
programmes in
collaboration with
universities across Europe

2. R&I Management Upskilling

Create a collaboration
framework for R&I proposals

Establish CORE IC's R&I
management unit

Develop a customised project
management tool

Design an interactive
Proposal-to-Project serious
game

4 F

AREAS

3. Business Development

Create a partnership programme to bridge industry and academia

Map out a best practice atlas for digital twin technologies in Europe

Develop the Greek Smart Factory business model

4. Research Project

Develop digital twins for an additive manufacturing use case

Validate Industry4.0 technologies through a test and demo platform

FOCUS

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Funded by
the European Union

TWIN4TWIN

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LinkedIn

Twin4Twin EU Project

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